

A Proposal for Self Assessment Scale: Meyar¹²

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Abstract

Establishing a scale and assessment, one of the most important elements of educational activities, plays a crucial role in determining the level of learning of the desired behaviour, knowledge, or concept by the other party. Establishing criteria is presented as a primary condition for learning gains; thus, the goal is to achieve learning in a fair and equal manner. This study proposes a new assessment model that leaves the criterion setting process to the learner, and allows learners to structure their own learning, manage their own learning processes, and evaluate themselves. Meyar is a process that begins with the request of the student who wants to learn the subject or concept to be learned. After learning the basic literature and main points related to the subject to be learned, students determine how, in what way, and at what level they will learn this subject; the advisor teacher supports the students in achieving the goals they have set for themselves during this process; and, at the end of the course and teaching, students measure their own success. The purpose and motivation of this model is for individuals to become aware of their learning needs by conducting their own assessments, thereby enabling learning to become a character trait that can be applied. This study thus anticipates that individuals' moral, personal, and academic development can be enhanced in a conscious manner. The study is conducted using theoretical analysis research methods.

Key Words: Education, Teaching, Assessment, Meyar, Self-Assessment

Introduction

Success, performance, and progress in a subject are prepared using an unchanging scale as a reference and evaluated accordingly. The reliability and validity of this measurement assessment is based on the fact that it provides an unchanging and objective result for the situation or object being measured. For example, the fact that a meter corresponds to the same standard value everywhere in the world is the most concrete example of this. Similarly, in an exam graded out of 100 points, the grades or scores students receive provide information about the planned learning outcomes, behaviours, and knowledge level for that course. In this sense, the measurement value and standard are quite important, as they indicate how well a targeted behavior aligns with a predefined behaviour (Demircan-Çakar et al, 2010). Based on this, the study argues that people can determine their own criteria and evaluate themselves. The study argues that individuals can evaluate themselves by referring to universal moral criteria. It is important to state that a society can be generated in terms of trusting individuals and their abilities

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² The study is an extended version of the paper presented to A Proposal for an Education and Teaching Assessment Scale: Meyar at 16-23 January Aicmes 9th International Conference On Scientific Studies.

as person can contribute to the world greatly (Göksoy, & M. Gökmen, 2024)The important point here is what behavior and knowledge will be measured and which theory or moral value will be used to test them.

1. Problem of the Study

It is now widely accepted that an ideal society can only be achieved by raising ideal individuals (Gükltekin, 2007). It has also been emphasized by the three Abrahamic religions and other humanistic religions that an ideal society cannot be separated from a life that prioritizes moral values (Crosby, 2018; King, 1984). Ultimately, a moral life and an ideal, happy, and peaceful life is a way of life that all people on earth, regardless of their different beliefs, commonly accept and desire (Arıcan, 2016). The basis for all religions recommending and advising this is the realization of a peaceful and just life in society. Based on this, the starting point of this study is that individuals can evaluate their own value systems based on a universal moral reference. It argues that when individuals begin to make their own assessments, an ideal society will emerge spontaneously, and that for a moral and just society, individuals must first hold themselves accountable.

2. Motivation of the Study

The importance of individuals evaluating themselves for a more just, equal, and happy world has been the motivation for this study (Em. Erdoğan, 2025; Gündoğdu, 2025). However, the existence of individuals who believe in themselves first, who do not harm others in what they do and will do, and who pay the utmost attention to this is crucial for the peace and happiness of a society (R.T. Erdoğan, 2025). Based on this, this study argues that individuals in an ideal society can evaluate themselves and, in doing so, feel more peaceful and happier. The fundamental reference point of this study is that individuals who complete their self-evaluation will have high self-esteem and will also provide significant benefits to the society in which they live (Hackett, 1995).

3. Methodology of the Study

The study aimed to develop Meyar using Robert Kohlberg's moral judgement criteria.

4. Development of Morality

Morality has a very long history and is the primary reference point for all religious and sociological theories and lifestyles (Chiang, 2011). Although moral development varies from society to society in this respect, societies share similar characteristics in terms of moral structure and practices (Gültekin, 2014). Socrates' understanding of morality was in line with Aristotle's, while the Hz. Muhammad's understanding of morality was in line with that of Hz. Moses and Hz. Jesus, and was a more developed form of them (Scott, 2000). The common term in all of them was that morality should first ensure justice and equality and then share a peaceful and ideal happiness. Al-Ghazali defined it this way, and Al-Farabi and Ibn Rushd; understood and applied it in the same vein (Al-Ghazali, 2010; Arıcan, 2008; Farabi, 2017). Even Sa'd Shirazi stated that ethics must be centred on justice, and Feriddun Attar and similarly argued that the development of ethics is necessary for the just and peaceful structure of societies (Attar, 2019; M. Gökmen, 2024; Şirazi, 2021). Although these individuals come from different geographical regions, time periods, and religious backgrounds, their views on ethics converge to a significant degree. This underscores the direct relationship between Morals and religion and way of life.

5. Meyar

A happy, secured and successful society cannot progress sustainably without prioritising moral and ethical values. Success built upon the labour and rights of others constitutes a significant violation of human rights, rejected by both divine and human religions (Jaffee, 2001). Islam defines this situation as the servant's right, and considers it so valuable that Allah will not arbitrate between people regarding the servant's right (Al-Qurtuby, 2013; Kalın, 2019). Islam wants the servant to take their right from the servant, and does not want reconciliation (Iqbal, 2012; Khel, 1985). This situation also requires the rights of servants to be realised in social life on an equal, just and equitable plane, both privately and publicly (Mevlana Celaleddin Rumi, 2015). This assessment stems from the fact that such an important issue is the result of a mindset that divides learning into two categories: positive sciences and religious sciences (Husain, 1984; Sezgin, 2008). While positive sciences focus on cause and effect with a rational and pragmatic mindset, religious sciences serve as a source of suggestions, advice and predictions about the possible consequences of behaviour before it occurs, in a preventive manner (İbni Haldun, 1977; Leiss, 1994). As the positive sciences focus on cause and effect, they do not consider moral development or duties when evaluating the moral or ethical development of successful individuals (İbni Rüşd, 2020).

They only consider the work itself, paying no attention to the individual (Itl, 1963). However, moral development should be fundamental to scientific studies (İzetbegoviç, 2012). It cannot be limited or regulated solely by rules and regulations, punishment or obedience; this approach is not sustainable (Arıcan, 2006; Karademir, 2018). Furthermore, punishments, whether direct or indirect, are ineffective in curbing behaviour, even if they temporarily suppress it (Seki, 1992). Therefore, it is very difficult for punishment or rules alone to regulate social life. For this reason, the importance of moral values and ethical approaches is becoming increasingly apparent (Göksoy, 2017). From this perspective, the focus is on evaluating and measuring how well moral patterns or sacred moral values can be applied by people who anticipate that students and individuals will design their own learning and personal development programmes and make their own assessments (Ibn Rushd, 2018; Piaget, 1971). The important thing here is that individuals or students design their own development according to a moral framework, religion or the moral teachings of the positive sciences, so that they can converge at a common point in social life (Ellwood, 1913; Tuğrul, & Aydın, 2023). Meyar attaches primary importance to the fact that these moral values do not conflict with other moral values (Selwyn, 2019). Rather than pitting moral teachings against each other, therefore, Meyar aims to contribute to the construction of the ideal human being, society and state by uniting them at a common point. The fact that individuals choose these moral values and evaluate themselves is also an indication of the necessity and importance of Meyar (Göksoy, 2017).

The study argues that individuals who create their own learning programmes and designs while contributing to society and not isolating themselves from social life, are important for social peace and tranquillity. It suggests that learners motivated by this should create their own learning according to their needs. Thus, the study focuses on students designing teaching activities for their chosen courses according to their preferences, after receiving an introductory lesson and information about the course content from the instructor (Durkheim, 1956). Similar to the portfolio creation activity, this process involves students creating evaluation criteria and using them to evaluate their own work. Subsequently, the student's cognitive, psychomotor and moral development is confirmed by the class checking the student's criteria and evaluations (Piaget, 1971). As the teacher is also involved in this final checking process, students who do not evaluate themselves according to ethical values or who find themselves lacking will be identified. These students will receive the score they gave themselves as a course grade, but this ethical violation

will be recorded in their academic records. This will create a record of the student's academic and ethical development. While students build their own success, their classmates and teachers will act as a control group, balancing their ethical and moral skills and behaviours. However, individuals may experience difficulties acting socially or within society if they are isolated from it. This will affect cognitive, social and psychomotor learning, as well as presentation and programme design skills (Piaget, 1971). Alongside the student's successful profile, a moral development report card will also be created. It is anticipated that, in the long term, social welfare and happiness can be achieved through the development of individuals who respect others, are loving and honest, and do not violate societal rights (Arıcan, 2011). Here, it is individuals' fair evaluations that ensure Meyer achieves its primary goal. Initially, students or individuals will establish a moral reference point for a course, teaching or programme that is religious and humanistic yet universally accepted, aligned with universal values and applied by societies (Göksoy, 2018). These values may be prescribed by Judaism, Christianity or Islam, or they may be based on Kohlberg's moral stages of development as defined by positive science (Kohlberg, 1981). Islam equally advises people to trust and respect each other (Demant, 2006; Imam Bukhari, 1994). The important thing here is the moral definitions and characteristics that individuals determine based on this reference point (M. Gökmen, & S. Gökmen, 2025). Once these values have been identified, individuals are expected to create a self-evaluation rubric. An example of this is as follows.

6.1. Meyer Application Sample:

Sample 1: The Structure of Meyer

Subject: Self-Assessment during my project studies

- 1. Reference:** Islam
- 2. Expected moral values:** Justice, Equality, Honesty, Respect, Courtesy
- 3. Specific references:** Surahs in the Quran where these values are mentioned: Surah Al-Baqarah, Surah Al-Hajj, Surah Al-Ma'idah, Ali 'Imran, Surah Isra, Al-Qiyamah.
- 4. Behavior Patterns Section**

4.1. During this project/lesson process, I maintained sincere and honest relationships with people. Neyzen and Semazen, with whom I communicated, expressed this as follows:

4.2. During this process, I conducted my relationships with the people I reached based on justice and equality. Gülak and Meşer, with whom I communicated, expressed this as follows:

4.3. I did confirm that during this process, and I did not mislead people in my statements: Turgut and Cihan with whom I communicated during this process, express this as follows:

4.4. During this process, I developed a sincere, polite, and courteous tone and behavior in my approach to those younger and older than me. Pusat and Tepak, with whom I communicated, express this as follows.

5. References

5.1. Neyzen conveyed this statement to me in writing on January 14, 2026, at 2:10 PM while we were working together in class.

5.2. Semazen stated this statement on January 16, 2026, at 5:01 p.m. upon my request.

5.3. Gülak conveyed this statement on January 17, 2026, at 6:30 p.m. while we were working on our project at school.

5.4. Meşer conveyed this statement to me by phone at 8:00 PM on January 18, 2026, and subsequently conveyed it to me online via message.

5.5. Turgut sent me this statement as a message at 12:05 PM on January 20, 2026, upon my request.

5.6. Cihan conveyed this statement to me in writing at my request on February 12, 2026, at 4:01 p.m.

5.7. Pusat conveyed this statement to me in writing at my request on February 14, 2026, at 10:02 a.m.

5.8. Tepak wrote this statement at my request on February 15, 2026, at 11:30 a.m. and handed it to me.

Note: All these source texts are included in the appendix of my work.

Sample 2: The Structure of Meyar

Self assessment during my thesis preparation with meyar

- 5. Reference:** Kohlberg's Moral values for a fair society
- 6. Expected moral values:** Fairness, equality, respect, kindness, and protecting people's dignity.
- 7. Specific references:** Kohlberg, L. (1981). The philosophy of moral development: Moral stages and the idea of justice. Harper & Row.
- 8. Behavior Patterns Section**

4.1. I declare that during my thesis process, I will use sources and conduct my work in accordance with Kohlberg's moral principles of fairness, equality, respect, kindness, and protecting people's dignity. I assessment myself over 100. I have five section for this part and each chapter is graded over % 20.

4.1.1. Fairness: At the beginning of my work, I reviewed the studies conducted in this field and examined the works published in this area, and I did not use anyone else's ideas in my work without citing them. The Ithenticate report serves as proof of this. 20 points

4.1.2. Equality: Throughout my work, I did not highlight any particular person's work, and I included both national and international sources in my work. In this respect, I acted in accordance with the principle of equality. In my bibliography, foreign sources are of equal value to Turkish sources. Since there are more foreign sources in this field, I had to consult foreign sources more than national sources. 17 points.

4.1.3. Respect: Throughout my work, I have indicated a proper reference system for thoughts and expressions that do not belong to me. In my work, I have not harmed any person, institution, or any object or entity in nature; I have protected the uniqueness that

everyone is born with throughout my work. The most important indicator of this is that the names and thoughts of the students included in my work are given under pseudonyms. Since I had to use a considerable amount of paper during my work, I deducted 5 points because I felt I had been a little disrespectful to nature. 15 points.

4.1.4. Kindness: Throughout my research, I used a polite and respectful tone with the people, institutions, colleagues, and my advisor involved in my work. I did not force anyone to do anything they did not want to do, and in cases of disagreement, I tried to resolve the issue; when I could not resolve it, I defined the problem and left it to the other party to find a solution. I deducted 6 points. This is because, despite using a polite tone throughout my research, I adopted a formal tone of speech instead of a polite one when dealing with difficult situations and individuals during the research period. In this regard, I cannot say that I maintained a polite tone throughout every stage of my work. 14 points

4.1.5. Protecting People's Dignity: Throughout my work, I have treated people and all living things on Earth with respect regarding their lives, expressions, and beliefs. I did not enforce anyone to follow any guidelines they did not want to follow, nor did I include any beliefs in my work that they did not express. Throughout my work, I have not engaged in any initiative that would harm any living being, especially humans, and I have performed the utmost respect for people's expression, existence, and thoughts throughout my research. When I encountered people and situations who did not share my views, I first tried to explain myself, then conveyed my thoughts to the other party. Whether the other party respected my thoughts or not, I did not change my attitude or behavior towards them. I deducted 6 points. However, throughout my work, I could not include all the views and thoughts that opposed my thesis, but I did not allow this because of the scope of my work and so as not to distort the clarity of the thought I defended. Although I included research that expressed views different from mine in my work, I could not include all opposing views in my research. From this perspective, I am deducting 6 points and awarding 14 points.

Total Score: In this study, I scored 80 points using Kohlberg's moral teachings of Fairness, equality, respect, kindness, and protecting people's dignity, along with my own scale and scoring system. This score was achieved through the argumentation provided by the scientific nature of my work and the intensive work process I underwent throughout the research.

5. References

5.8.

Note: All these source texts are included in the appendix of my work.

Conclusion

Self-assessment is an important aspect of ethical behavior. However, the extent to which a person can accurately and fairly assess themselves is a significant issue in itself. However, establishing a scale for self-evaluation and assessing oneself according to this scale is an important practice and indicator of ethical behavior. Establishing one's own evaluation criteria by specifying a reference point and assessing oneself accordingly will ensure the application of important values in society such as justice, respect, honesty, and ethical judgment, much like how small details form the big picture. It is important for a person to be able to evaluate themselves first and to create their own value assessment chart according to a reference point stated at the outset, both in terms of forming their own behavior pattern and increasing their self-respect. This work and perspective, which will also make an important contribution to society in the big picture, will contribute to the spread of moral values in society. However, whether it is Kohlberg, Islamic, Jewish, or Christian moral values, since they all assert that human beings are unique, valuable, and important, this study predicts that there will be no significant difference between moral teachings and definitions.

However, Buddhism or other humanistic religions can also be cited as examples of these references, which are essentially about creating ideal and good people. What is important here is that the reference point determined by the individual should be values that are recognized and acceptable by society and academic literature; otherwise, individuals' personal expectations or character patterns will limit the movement and purpose of the reference point, ensuring that individuals in society are ideal individuals created from only one point of view. From this

perspective, the application of universal values and reference points for the yardstick will ensure the formation of a generation that is more respectful, courteous, and respectful of moral values, both for individuals and societies, as well as for the long-term future. This will enable people to evaluate themselves according to the scale they have created and to exercise their own self-control. The success of individuals who exercise self-control will also ensure a more peaceful and secure society.

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New Glossaries For Turkish and English Languages

1. ***Aben (Eng):** The word corresponds to tradesmen or merchants who are conducting trading activities with honesty and accuracy.
 - 1.1. **Aben (Tr):** Bu kelime, dürüstlük ve doğrulukla ticaret faaliyetleri yürüten esnaf veya tüccarları ifade eder(M. Gökmen).
2. ***Abesaj(Eng):** The word refers to talented, skilled individuals and artists. The word also has the meaning of being able and capable of doing something or a task.
 - 2.1. **Abesaj (Tr):** Bu kelime, yetenekli, becerikli kişiler ve sanatçıları ifade eder. Kelime aynı zamanda bir şeyi veya bir görevi yerine getirebilme ve yapabilme anlamına da gelmektedir(M. Gökmen).
3. ***Aderes (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are kind, naive and helpful in their attitudes. The word is synonym to lady and gentleman.
 - 3.1. **Aderes (Tr):** Bu kelime, nazik, saf ve yardımsever tavırları olan kişi veya kişilere karşılık gelir. Bu kelime, hanımefendi ve beyefendi ile eş anlamlıdır(M. Gökmen).
4. ***Aket (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who support an argument with strong proof, clue and claim.
 - 4.1. **Aket (Tr):** Kelime bir düşünceyi açıklamak, ayrıntılandırmak ve bir konuda bir farklı bir sav ya da fikir ileri sürmek anlamına gelmektedir(M. Gökmen).
5. ***Aknis(Eng):** The word is synonym to mother.
 - 5.1. **Aknis (Tr):** Bu kelime anne ile eş anlamlıdır(M. Gökmen).
6. ***Akpuz (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are fair, trustable and pleasant.
 - 6.1. **Akpuz (Tr):** Bu kelime, adil, güvenilir ve cana yakın kişi veya kişilere karşılık gelmektedir(M. Gökmen).
7. ***Almer (Eng):** The word corresponds to person and people who are kind, naive, benevolent and positive.
 - 7.1. **Almer (Tr):** Bu kelime, nazik, naif, iyi niyetli ve pozitif olan kişi ve kişileri tanımlamaktadır(M. Gökmen).
8. ***Alpeş (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are friendly.

- 8.1. Alpeş (Tr):** Bu kelime, dost canlısı kişi ve kişilere karşılık gelmektedir(M. Gökmen).
- 9. *Atamak (Eng):** The word corresponds to consistent and clear person or people.
- 9.1. Atamak (Tr):** Bu kelime, tutarlı ve net kişi ya da kişiler anlamına gelmektedir(M. Gökmen).
- 10. *Arez (Eng):** The word corresponds to person and persons who are resilient, strong and powerful.
- 10.1. Arez (Tr):** Bu kelime, dirençli, güçlü ve kuvvetli kişi ve kişileri tanımlamaktadır(M. Gökmen).
- 11. *Arşen (Eng):** The word is synonym to partner and friend.
- 11.1. Arşen (Tr):** Bu kelime, ortak ve arkadaş ile eş anlamlıdır(M. Gökmen).
- 12. *Asbaç (Eng):** The word refers to a person or persons who are compatible with their community in term of contributing to the development of the community while maintaining their distinguish identities.
- 12.1. *Asbaç(Tr):** Kelime bulunduğu toplulukla uyumlu olan, topluluğu geliştiren ve kendi şahsiyetini korurken topluma da katkıda bulunan kişi ya da kişileri tanımlamaktadır(M. Gökmen).
- 13. *Atan(Eng):** The word is synonym to father.
- 13.1. Atan (Tr):** Bu kelime, baba ile eş anlamlıdır(M. Gökmen).
- 14. *Babel/ Babelisation (Eng):** This word is inspired by the Tower of Babel. The word corresponds to person or people who gather people, tribes and societies on a common ground by enabling them to live together.
- 14.1. Babellemek (Tr):** Kelime Babil Kulesinden esenlenerek türetilmiştir. İnsanları, kabileleri, toplumları bir arada ortak paydada toplamak ve onları bir arada yaşamalarını sağlama anlamına gelmektedir (M. Gökmen).
- 15. *Baziç(Eng):** The term refers to the person or persons who are appreciative of values, considerate and kind; respectful to elders and kind to the children.
- 15.1. Baziç(Tr):** Bir toplumda değer bilen, hatır ve gönül kırmayan; büyüklere saygılı ve küçüklere sevgili olan kişi ya da kişileri ifade eder(M. Gökmen).
- 16. *Belif (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are trying to be Allah's sincere, righteous, beloved servant. The word also corresponds to being self-sufficient by

not harming anyone while pursuing a life aligned with Allah's advices. The word also corresponds to person or people who are acting as the servant of people in order to gain Allah's consent.

16.1. Belif (Tr): Kelime Allah'ın halis, muhlis, iyi kulu anlamına gelmektedir. Kelime aynı zamanda kendi halinde olma durumu için de kullanılır. Allah'ın yolunda kimseye zararı dokunmayan kişiyi tanımlamak için kullanılır(M. Gökmen).

17. *Belirmat (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who represent, demonstrate and illustrate something or a substance. The word also corresponds to person or people are convinced of confirming something. The word is synonym to representation.

17.1. Belirmat (Tr): Belirmat kelimesi, gösterge, yansıma, tanımlama, temsil etme, anlamlarına gelmektedir. Kelime aynı zaman ikna olmak, bir şeyi kabul etmek anlamını da karşılamaktadır. Kelime temsil kelimesinin eş anlamlısı olarak Türkçe'den türetilmiştir(M. Gökmen).

18. *Beydin (Eng): The word corresponds to young people. The word also corresponds to tiny one floor house, hut, single-story house.

18.1. . Beydin (Tr): Kelime genç insanları tanımlamaktadır. Aynı zamanda kelime küçük, tek katlı bina, kulübe ve ev anlamına gelmektedir(M. Gökmen).

19. *Bilkadir (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who are acting as the director of a scientific, research and educational institution. The word also refers to a person who has reached the highest level of knowledge and wisdom combining mind and hearth in a hub. The word is synonymous to loyalty and faithful. Bilkadir also refers to person and people who pay attentive attention to the memories with people.

19.1. Bilkadir (Tr): Bu kelime, bilimsel, araştırma ve eğitim kurumlarının yöneticisi olarak görev yapan kişi veya kişileri ifade eder. Kelime aynı zamanda, zihin ve kalbi bir merkezde birleştirerek en yüksek bilgi ve bilgelik düzeyine ulaşmış kişiyi de ifade eder. Kelime, sadakat ve bağlılık ile eş anlamlıdır. Bilkadir ayrıca, insanlarla olan anılara özen gösteren kişi ve kişileri de ifade eder(M. Gökmen).

20. *Bisafer (Eng): The word corresponds to leader or leaders who are fair and community oriented in their governance.

20.1. Bisafer (Tr): Bu kelime, adil ve toplum odaklı yönetim sergileyen lider veya liderleri tanımlamaktadır(M. Gökmen).

- 21. *Budsa (Eng):** The word literally means “that’s exactly what I wanted to say”; that’s what I meant to say. The word is synonym to indeed, of course, sure.
- 21.1. Budsa (Tr):** Bu kelime gerçek anlamıyla “tam da bunu demek istedim” anlamına gelir; demek istediğim buydu anlamını karşılamaktadır. Bu kelime, gerçekten, elbette, tabii ki kelimelerinin eşanlamlısıdır(M. Gökmen).
- 22. *Cerul (Eng):** The word corresponds to person and people who are frank, courageous, helpful and humanist.
- 22.1. Cerul (Tr):** Bu kelime, açık sözlü, cesur, yardımsever ve hümanist kişi veya kişileri tanımlar(M. Gökmen).
- 23. Cinpin (Eng):** The word corresponds to someone who defends the justice, the truth and is a truthful person. The word also means someone who is confident and trustworthy.
- 23.1. Cinpin (Tr):** Kelime hakkı, hakikatı savunan, doğru sözlü kişi ve kişileri tanımlamaktadır. Kelime ayrıca güven veren kişiler için de kullanılabilir(M. Gökmen).
- 24. *Çobar (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are tidy, neat, clean and pure in their thought.
- 24.1. Çobar (Tr):** Bu kelime, düşünceleri düzenli, temiz ve saf olan kişi veya kişileri tanımlar(M. Gökmen).
- 25. *Daçari (Eng):**The word is synonym to moreover, furthermore, therefore. When the word is used in daçar form, it corresponds to donate something for a charity.
- 25.1. Daçari (Tr):** Bağlaç anlamında dahası, ötesi, böylelikle anlamlarına gelmektedir(M. Gökmen).
- 26. *Danafer (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are sympathetic, entertaining, cheerful, and helpful.
- 26.1. Danafer (Tr):** Kelime çevresine karşı sempatik, eğlenceli, neşeli ve yardımsever kişileri tanımlamaktadır(M. Gökmen).
- 27. *Dasem (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are free-spirited, independent, sovereign. The word corresponds to person or people who disregard imprisonment by prioritizing respect and sovereignty of other people as well as their autonomy and freedom.

- 27.1. Dasem(Tr):** Kelime özgür ruhlu, özgürlüğüne düşkün, başına buyruk anlamına gelmektedir. Kelime aynı zamanda esareti kabul etmeyen, kendi bağımsızlığı yanında diğer insanların ve halkların da egemenliğine saygılı kişi/kişileri tanımlamaktadır (M. Gökmen).
- 28. *Desak (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are cautious, calm, serene, and peaceful.
- 28.1. Desak (Tr):** Kelime tedbirli, sakin, dingin ve huzurlu anlamına gelmektedir (M. Gökmen).
- 29. *Defay (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are entrepreneur.
- 29.1. Defay (Tr):** Bu kelime, girişimci olan kişi ya da kişileri tanımlar (M. Gökmen).
- 30. *Devçel (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who donate or share something without any expectation. The word is synonym to generous.
- 30.1. Devçel (Tr):** Bu kelime, hiçbir beklentiye sahip olmadan bir şey bağışlayan veya paylaşan kişi veya kişileri tanımlamaktadır. Bu kelime, cömert kelimesinin eşanlamlısıdır (M. Gökmen).
- 31. *Dilaz (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are worthless and insignificant. The is also synonym to cheap and meaningless.
- 31.1. Dilaz (Tr):** Bu kelime, değersiz ve önemsiz kişi veya kişiler tanımlar. Kelime aynı zamanda ucuz ve anlamsız kelimeleriyle eşanlamlıdır (M. Gökmen).
- 32. *Diyruz (Eng):** The word means to listen attentively to a person or people; share their feelings by supporting them. The word is synonymous to empathy.
- 32.1. Diyruz (Tr):** Bu kelime, bir kişiye veya kişilere dikkatle dinlemek; onları destekleyerek duygularını paylaşmak anlamına gelir. Bu kelime empati ile eş anlamlıdır (M. Gökmen).
- 33. Dönev (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who return to their starting point. The word also corresponds to person or people who turn back to their homes.
- 33.1. Dönev (Tr):** Kelime başlangıç noktasına, başlanılan noktaya geri dönmek anlamına gelmektedir. Kelime ayrıca bir şeyi eski haline döndürmek ve çevirmek anlamına da gelmektedir(M. Gökmen).
- 34. Egat (Eng):** The word literally refers to flourishing, cultivating, nurturing, putting in effort, and showing diligence for somebody or somethings to grow.

- 34.1. Egat (Tr):** Bu kelime, birinin veya bir şeyin büyümesi için çaba sarf etmek, yetiştirmek, beslemek, emek vermek ve gayret göstermek anlamına gelmektedir (M. Gökmen).
- 35. Eklım / Eklımısatıon (Eng.):** The word corresponds to person or people who lay the foundations of a thing or a phenomenon. Although eklım is from the same word family with articulation, it corresponds to initial state of articulation
- 35.1. Eklımleme (Tr):** Bir şeyin, olgunun temellerını atma, ona ilk şeklini verme ve onun temel yapı taşıını oluşturma. Eklemlleme ile aynı kelime aile grubundan olsa da burada eklımleme eklemllemeden önceki durumu, özü ve ilk halin şekillenmesi anlamına gelmektedir (Prof. Dr. Süleyman Göksoy, & Lect. Murat Gökmen).
- 36. Elızeb (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are generous, devoted, hardworking, noble, tolerant, helpful, optimist, cheerful, kind and humble
- 36.1. Elızeb (Tr)** Kelime cömert, fedakar, çalışkan, asil, anlayışlı, anaç, yardımsever, iyimser gülyüzlü, nazık, alçak gönüllü kışi ya da kışileri tanımlamak için kullanılır(M. Gökmen).
- 37. Emak (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are eminerten, gülseyan, teniz, enrahim, sebut, belif, semay, sincere, positive and constructive in her/his/their relations with people.
- 37.1. Emak (Tr):** Bu kelime, insanlarla ilişkilerinde eminerten, gülseyan, teniz, enrahim, sebut, belif, semay, samimi, olumlu ve yapıcı olan kışi veya kışilere karşılık gelir (M. Gökmen).
- 38. Eminerten (Eng):** The word corresponds to a person or people who are positive and patient when confronted with a problem or an obstacle. Eminerten people are dealing with problems with perseverance. The word also corresponds to person or people who entrust a task to Allah after doing everything that can be done by them. However, the word eminerten can also be used for the circumstances when a person or people starts another task after finishing their tasks without delay.
- 38.1. Eminerten (Tr):** Bu kelime, bir sorun veya engelle karşılaştıklarında olumlu ve sabırlı olan kışi veya kışileri ifade eder. Eminerten insanlar sorunlarla azimle başa çıkmaktadır. Bu kelime, yapabileceği her şeyi yaptıktan sonra bir görevi Allah'a emanet eden kışi veya kışilere de karşılık gelir. Ancak eminerten kelimesi, kışi veya

kişilerin görevlerini gecikmeden bitirdikten sonra başka bir göreve başladıkları durumlar için de kullanılabilir (M. Gökmen).

39. Enrahim (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who rely on Allah's justice in their deeds. The word is synonym to eminerten.

39.1. Enrahim (Tr): Kelime Allah'ın adaletine ve takdirine sığınma anlamına gelmektedir. Kelime eminerten ile eş anlamlıdır(M. Gökmen).

40. Ereb (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who are tolerant, honest, trustworthy. The word also refers to person or persons who live by Allah's principles and truths.

40.1. Ereb (Tr): Bu kelime, hoşgörülü, dürüst ve güvenilir kişi veya kişileri ifade eder. Bu kelime aynı zamanda Allah'ın ilkeleri ve gerçeklerine göre yaşayan kişi veya kişileri de ifade eder. (M. Gökmen)

41. Ermev (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who do not give priority to the worldly things and spends his wealth for the sake of Allah to the people in need of.

41.1. Ermev (Tr): Bu kelime, dünyevi şeylere öncelik vermeyen ve servetini Allah rızası için muhtaç insanlara harcayan kişi veya kişileri tanımlar (M. Gökmen).

42. Fesun (Eng): The word refers to person or persons who are steadfast, truthful, fair, self-sacrificing, and hardworking.

42.1. Fesun (Tr): Bu kelime, kararlı, dürüst, adil, özverili ve çalışkan kişi veya kişileri ifade eder (M. Gökmen).

43. Felos (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who are successful and beautiful. The word also corresponds to person or people who have a good and effective odour.

43.1. Felos (Tr): Bu kelime, başarılı ve güzel olan kişi veya kişileri ifade etmektedir.M. Gökmen).

44. Figed (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who conduct their researches as their profession. The word is synonym to scientist and scholar.

44.1. Figed (Tr): Bu kelime, araştırmalarını meslek olarak yürüten kişi veya kişiler için kullanılır. Kelime, bilim insanı ve akademisyen ile eş anlamlıdır (M. Gökmen).

45. Gaztab (Eng): The word corresponds to person or persons who are quick and practical in their works.

- 45.1. Gaztab (Tr):** Bu kelime, işlerinde hızlı ve pratik olan kişi veya kişileri tanımlar (M. Gökmen).
- 46. Gotal (Eng):** The word corresponds to person and people who are well-intentioned, hardworking, successful, knowledgeable in science, art and literature. The word corresponds to person and people who share their knowledge without hesitation with the people. Gotal also refers to leaders who are moderate and fair in their offices.
- 46.1. Gotal (Tr):** Bu kelime, iyi niyetli, çalışkan, başarılı, bilim, sanat ve edebiyat konusunda bilgili kişi ve insanları ifade eder. Bu kelime, bilgilerini tereddüt etmeden insanlarla paylaşan kişi ve insanları ifade eder. Gotal ayrıca, görevlerinde ılımlı ve adil olan liderleri de ifade eder (M. Gökmen).
- 47. Gülak (Eng):** The word corresponds to being grateful, thankful and indebted for an occasion, specific person or people(M. Gökmen).
- 47.1. Gülak (Tr):** Bu kelime, bir olay, belirli bir kişi veya kişiler için minnettar, şükran dolu ve borçlu olmak anlamına gelir (M. Gökmen).
- 48. Güldef: (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are thankful and glad.
- 48.1. Güldef: (Tr):** Bu kelime, minnettar ve mutlu olan kişi veya kişileri tanımlamaktadır (M. Gökmen).
- 49. Gülseyen (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are noble, dignified, cheerful, peaceful, self-assured, determined and are in harmony with their environments. There is not an exact equivalent of this word in Turkish and English languages. Gülseyen is a person who combines confidence, content with humility in their manners.
- 49.1. Gülseyen (Tr):** Kelime asil, vakur, kendinden emin, kararlı, etrafıyla uyumlu, güleç ve huzurlu kişileri tanımlamaktadır. Gülyüzlü, neşeli anlamlarına gelen gülseyen vakur ve kendinden emin duruşunu tevazu tavırları karakterinde birleştiren nevişahsına münhasır kişi anlamında (M. Gökmen).
- 50. Ğazur (Eng):** The word is synonymous to garden, bostan, orchard.
- 50.1. Ğazur (Tr):** Bu kelime bahçe, bostan, meyve bahçesi ile eş anlamlıdır (M. Gökmen).
- 51. Ğepir (Eng):** The word is a synonym to presenter and announcer.
- 51.1. Ğepir (Tr):** Bu kelime, sunucu ve spiker ile eş anlamlıdır (M. Gökmen).
- 52. Ğibis (Eng):** The word is synonymous to happy and peaceful.

- 52.1. Ğibis (Tr):** Bu kelime mutlu ve huzurlu ile eř anlamlıdır (M. Gökmen).
- 53. Ğisan/Ğisen (Eng):** The word is synonym to expensive and precious.
- 53.1. Ğisen (Tr):** Bu kelime pahalı ve deęerli ile eř anlamlıdır (M. Gökmen).
- 54. Ğoleni (Eng):** The word describes a helpful and pleasing person or persons.
- 54.1. Ğoleni (Tr):** Bu kelime, yardımsever ve mutlu kiři veya kiřileri tanımlar (M. Gökmen).
- 55. Ğölin (Eng):** The word is synonym to talented.
- 55.1. Ğölin (Tr):** Bu kelime yetenekli ile eř anlamlıdır (M. Gökmen).
- 56. Ğuzen(Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are tall and powerful.
- 56.1. Ğuzen (Tr):** Bu kelime, uzun boylu, güçlü kiři ya da kiřileri tanımlamaktadır (M. Gökmen).
- 57. Ğünis (Eng):** The word is synonym to fertility and productive(M. Gökmen).
- 57.1. Ğünis (Tr):** Bu kelime, bereketlilik ve üretkenlik ile eř anlamlıdır (M. Gökmen).
- 58. Hamab (Eng):** The word refers to person or people who are devoted to their faiths. The word corresponds to person and people who support Allah's truth. The word also corresponds to person or people who live and act as the defender of the truth by following Allah's path.
- 58.1. Hamab (Tr):** Kelime dinine, diyanetine baęlı, hakkı, hakikati savunan; Allah'ın yolunda yařayan doęrunun savunucusu anlamına gelmektedir(M. Gökmen)
- 59. Hameç (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are loyal, devoted and self-sacrificing. Hameç people are known for their good deeds and generous contribution to their environments.
- 59.1. Hameç (Tr):** Kelime vefalı, vefakar, cefakar, etrafına faydalı olan; iyi iřlerle anılan ve hizmet üreten hayırsever kiři ya da kiřiler için kullanılır (M. Gökmen).
- 60. Hanya (Eng):** The word corresponds to big house.
- 60.1. Hanya (Tr):** Bu kelime büyük ev anlamına gelmektedir (M. Gökmen).
- 61. Hatan (Eng):** This word generated as an alternative vocabulary to gender studies taking its root from Hakan and Hatun in Turkish Language. Hatan as a new terminology prioritizes fair and decent society by supporting to give equal and fair opportunities for the sexes. This terminology emphasizes fair and equal status of the sexes in a society without prioritizing one over another. Hatan suggests a fair social status for the sexes in terms of daily and

working life tasks. Hatan suggests that regardless of biological sexes people according to their preferences, capacities, talents and characteristics align with their biology can do any task that they want to do. Therefore, for Hatan, there is not a predefined role attained for the sexes. Hatan fosters equal and fair distribution of roles in the society by prioritizing intellectual capacity of the parties. Fairness for Hatan is prior to equality.

61.1. Hatan (Tr): Bu kelime, Türkçe'deki Hakan ve Hatun kelimelerinden kök alan, toplumsal cinsiyet çalışmalarına alternatif bir kelime olarak ortaya çıkmıştır. Yeni bir terim olan Hatan, cinsiyetler arasında eşit ve adil fırsatlar sunulmasını destekleyerek adil ve ahlaklı bir toplumu önceliklendirir. Bu terim, toplumda cinsiyetler arasında adil ve eşit bir statüye öncelik verirken, herhangi birini diğerine göre öncelikli konumda tutmamaktadır. Hatan, günlük yaşam ve iş hayatındaki görevler açısından cinsiyetler için adil bir sosyal statü önermektedir. Hatan, biyolojik cinsiyetlerinden bağımsız olarak, insanların tercihlerine, yeteneklerine, becerilerine ve biyolojilerine uygun özelliklerine göre istedikleri herhangi bir görevi yapabileceklerini önermektedir. Bu nedenle, Hatan için cinsiyetler için önceden belirlenmiş bir rol yoktur. Hatan, tarafların entelektüel kapasitelerine öncelik vererek toplumda rollerin adil ve eşit dağılımını teşvik eder. Hatan için adalet, eşitlikten önce gelmektedir (M. Gökmen).

62. Hüs(z)dal (Eng): The word refers to bringing or presenting something.

62.1. Hüs(z)dal (Tr): Bu kelime, bir şeyi getirmek veya sunmak anlamına gelir (M. Gökmen)

63. İlaz (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who are valuable, precious. The word is also synonym to expensive(M. Gökmen).

63.1. İlaz (Tr): Bu kelime, değerli, kıymetli kişi veya kişileri tanımlamaktadır. Kelime aynı zamanda pahalı kelimesinin eş anlamlısıdır (M. Gökmen).

64. İsyak (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who are devote her/his/ their life to Allah and live according to Allah's fairness, justice and equality. The word is synonym to dervish in Turkish.

64.1. İsyak (Tr): Bu kelime, hayatını Allah'a adayan ve Allah'ın adalet, hakkaniyet ve eşitlik ilkelerine göre yaşayan kişi veya kişileri ifade eder. Bu kelime, Türkçe'de derviş ile eş anlamlıdır (M. Gökmen).

- 65. Janik (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are beautiful, pleasant and easygoing (M. Gökmen).
- 65.1. Janik (Tr):** Bu kelime, güzel, hoş ve uyumlu kişi veya kişileri ifade eder (M. Gökmen).
- 66. Kadmer (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are innovative, broad-minded and thoughtful.
- 66.1. Kadmer (Tr.):** Kelime yenilikçi, ufku geniş, açık düşünceli ve görüşlü kişi ya da kişileri tanımlamaktadır (M. Gökmen).
- 67. Kayşe (Eng):** The word corresponds to sincere, trustable, kind and witty person and people.
- 67.1. Kayşe (Tr):** Kelime samimi, güven veren, kibar ve mantıklı kişi ve kişileri tanımlamaktadır(M. Gökmen).
- 68. Keysan (Eng):** The word designates a person or persons who organize and plan their affairs or works.
- 68.1. Keysan (Tr):** Bu kelime, işlerini veya çalışmalarını organize eden ve planlayan kişi veya kişileri tanımlar (M. Gökmen).
- 69. Közek (Eng):** The word refers to people who are smart and have good looking.
- 69.1. Közek (Tr):** Bu kelime, zeki, yakışıklı ve güzel insanları ifade eder (M. Gökmen).
- 70. Maben (Eng):** The word corresponds to merchant or merchants who carry out their commercial activities dishonestly. The word is antonym to aben.
- 70.1. Maben (Tr):** Bu kelime, ticari faaliyetlerini dürüst olmayan bir şekilde yürüten tüccar veya tüccarlara karşılık gelir. Bu kelime, aben kelimesinin zıttıdır (M. Gökmen).
- 71. Makpuz (Eng):** The word is used for uncertain and ambiguous situations.
- 71.1. Makpuz (Tr):** Kelimer belirsiz ve muğlak durumlar için kullanılır. (M. Gökmen).
- 72. Maroj (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are knowledgeable, attentive, sympathetic, thoughtful, tolerant with a positive attitude towards people and life.
- 72.1. Maroj (Tr):** Kelime bilgili, ilgili, sempatik, düşünceli, anlayışlı ve hayata pozitif bakmak anlamlarına gelmekte olup bu kişileri tanımlamaktadır (M. Gökmen).
- 73. Medalime (Eng):** The word refers to an educational institution, academy or a curriculum;
- Medalim: (Eng):** The word defines scholars who teach and conduct research at Medalime;

Medal (Eng): The word is synonym to scientific studies; **Medali (Eng):** The word is synonym to article and essay; **Medale(Eng):** The word is synonym to project, thesis and book; **Medalet(Eng):** The word corresponds to shorter and limited version of an article.

73.1. Medalime (Tr): Eğitim kurumu, eğitim müessesesi, kurum ve müfredat anlamlarına gelmektedir. **Medalim(Tr):** Bu kurumda ders veren ve araştırma yapan kişileri tanımlamaktadır. **Medal(Tr):** Bu kurumda üretilen bilimsel çalışmaların genel ismi. **Medali(Tr):** kapsamlı bir yayın, kitap, proje gibi. **Medale(Tr):** Makale gibi sistemli bir şekilde bir argümanı ve ifadeyi savunan araştırma. **Medalet(Tr):** Makalenin daha kısa ve sınırlı halidir (M. Gökmen).

74. Mekif (Eng): The word corresponds to person, people who are courageous, logical and wise. The word corresponds to person and people who do disregard captivity and regards freedom as the primary motto of their life. The word is synonymous with Mujahid and Nefek.

74.1. Mekif (Tr): Bu kelime, cesur, mantıklı ve bilge olan kişi ya da kişileri ifade eder. Kelime, esareti kabul etmeyen ve özgürlüğü birincil ilke olarak gören kişi ya da kişileri tanımlar(M. Gökmen).

75. Mercit (Eng): This word refers to person or persons who are rational and analytical in their attitudes.

75.1. Mercit (Tr): Bu kelime, tutumlarında analitik ve rasyonel olan kişi veya kişileri tanımlar (M. Gökmen).

76. Mesber (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who work and serve in a particular field or an area with great effort. The word corresponds to person or people who dedicate themselves to the society they live in. The word is synonym to altruism

76.1. Mesber (Tr): Kelime emek veren, çalışan, bir konuda ya da alanda hizmette bulunan, topluma kendisini adayan kişi ya da kişileri tanımlamak adına türetilmiştir. Kelime Türkçe’de diğerkam ve fedakâr kelimeleriyle eş anlamlıdır (M. Gökmen).

77. Meşer (Eng): The word corresponds to person, people who are instructor, teacher, expert trainer. The word is synonymous to yusek and teacher.

77.1. Meşer (Tr): Bu kelime, eğitmen, öğretmen, uzman eğitmen olan kişi veya kişileri tanımlamaktadır. Bu kelime, yusek ve öğretmen kelimeleriyle eş anlamlıdır (M. Gökmen).

78. Meyar (Eng): The word refers to the person, people who objectively determine their own education and training program requirements and deficiencies objectively by self-assessing themselves.

78.1. Meyar (Tr): Bu kelime, kendi eğitim ve öğretim programı gereksinimlerini ve eksikliklerini objektif olarak belirleyen, kendini değerlendiren kişileri ifade eder (M. Gökmen).

79. Mizif (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who conduct their attitudes with intellect and consciousness.

79.1. Mizif (Tr): Kelime akıllı, bilinçli, farkındalık düzeyi yüksek kişileri tanımlamak adına türetilmiştir (M. Gökmen).

80. Mubay (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who protect precious treasure, culture, language or religion of a community.

80.1. Mubay (Tr): Mubay kelimesi, çok değerli, kıymetli bir hazineyi, kültürü, dili, dini, insanın önem atfettiği en değerli varlığın korunması anlamına gelmektedir. Bu değerli varlık kişi, kurum, dil, kültür, hazine, varlık, din, yer, mekân, düşünce, fikir olabilir (M. Gökmen).

81. Muhaz (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who are courageous.

81.1. Muhaz (Tr): Bu kelime, cesur kişi ya da kişileri tanımlamaktadır (M. Gökmen).

82. Musbey (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who are proud, determined, confident, visionary, farsighted, well-mannered, conscious, and rational in their manners

82.1. Musbey (Tr): Kelime gururlu, kararlı, kendinden emin, ileri görüşlü, vizyon sahibi, oturaklı, oturmasını kalkmasını bilen, bilinçli, mantıklı kişi ya da kişileri tanımlamaktadır (M. Gökmen).

83. Nacer (Eng): The word corresponds to carving the potential of a person or a community. The word corresponds to person or people who cultivate and teach people or community by enabling them to feel self-sufficient. The word is synonym to carving a mine, path and way.

83.1. Nacer (Tr): Kelime bir nesnenin ya da kişinin potansiyelini ortaya çıkarmak, onu eğitmek, işlemek ve onun kendisini yeterli hissetmesini sağlamak anlamına gelmektedir (M. Gökmen).

84. Nazut (Eng): The word corresponds to confident, trustable and polite person and people.

- 84.1. Nazut (Tr):** Bu kelime, kendine güvenen, güvenilir ve kibar kişi ve kişiler ifade eder (M. Gökmen).
- 85. Nefek (Eng):** The word corresponds to person and people who are determined and committed. The word also corresponds to person and people who are successful in literature, art and science. Furthermore, the word also corresponds to person and people are determined to support the truth by sharing their thought fearlessly. The word is synonym to MasterChef.
- 85.1. Nefek (Tr):** Bu kelime, kararlı ve adanmış kişi ve insanları ifade eder. Bu kelime aynı zamanda edebiyat, sanat ve bilim alanlarında başarılı kişi ve insanları da ifade eder. Ayrıca, bu kelime düşüncelerini korkusuzca paylaşarak gerçeği savunmaya kararlı kişi veya kişileri de tanımlar. Bu kelime Üstad ile eş anlamlıdır (M. Gökmen).
- 86. Nilener (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who tidy up, arrange, assemble things or people.
- 86.1. Nilener (Tr):** Kelime toparlayan, düzenleyen, bir araya getiren kişi ya da kişileri tanımlamaktadır (M. Gökmen).
- 87. Nistuç (Eng):** The word corresponds to good and nice. The word also corresponds to person or people who are good willing and helpful (M. Gökmen).
- 87.1. Nistuç (Tr):** Bu kelime, iyi ve güzel anlamına gelir. Kelime aynı zamanda iyi niyetli ve yardımsever kişi veya kişiler anlamına da gelmektedir (M. Gökmen).
- 88. Pamar (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are masters of their words with altruism. The word also corresponds to person or people who motivate people listen to him/her attentively. The word is synonym to orator.
- 88.1. Pamar (Tr):** Bu kelime, sözünün eri olan ve özverili kişileri tanımlamakta kullanılır. Kelime aynı zamanda, insanları kendisini dikkatle dinlemeye motive eden kişileri de tanımlamaktadır. Bu kelime, hatip kelimesinin eş anlamlısıdır (M. Gökmen).
- 89. Payeş (Eng):** The word refers to fair and equal share of the individuals' or communities' experiences without the predominance of one over another by contributing their development.
- 89.1. Payeş (Tr):** Bu kelime, bireylerin veya toplumların deneyimlerinin, birinin diğerine üstünlük taslamadan birbirlerinin gelişimlerine katkıda bulunarak adil ve eşit

bir şekilde paylaşılmasını ifade eder (Prof. Dr. Süleyman Göksoy & Lect. Murat Gökmen).

90. Puteş (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who are determined, and difficult to persuade. The word also corresponds to person or people who do not like to talk much. The word also corresponds to traditional person or people

90.1. Puteş (Tr): Bu kelime, kararlı ve ikna edilmesi zor kişi veya kişileri tanımlamaktadır. Kelime aynı zamanda, fazla konuşmayı sevmeyen kişi veya kişileri tanımlamak için de kullanılır. Kelime ayrıca geleneksel kişi veya kişileri de ifade etmektedir (M. Gökmen).

91. Pusak (Eng). The word is synonymous with obvious, clear, clean, pure, and untainted.

91.1. Pusak (Tr). Bu kelime, açık, net, temiz, saf ve lekesiz anlamlarına eşdeğerdir (M. Gökmen).

92. Pürgez (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who are beautiful, pretty and naïve. The word is synonym to easygoing, beautiful and janik.

92.1. Pürgez (Tr): Bu kelime, güzel, hoş ve saf olan kişi veya kişileri ifade eder. Bu kelime, rahat, güzel ve janik kelimelerinin eşanlamlısıdır (M. Gökmen).

93. Rekem (Eng): The word corresponds to person and people who are magnificent, tremendous, elegant, exquisite and marvelous (M. Gökmen).

93.1. Rekem (Tr): Bu kelime, muhteşem, olağanüstü, zarif, enfes ve harika olan kişi ve kişiler için kullanılır (M. Gökmen).

94. Resdal (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who are acting as messenger, ambassador and courier. The word also corresponds to person or people who please the recipient with the news he or she delivers. The word also corresponds to people who bring something new into community.

94.1. Resdal (Tr): Bu kelime, haberci, elçi ve kurye olarak görev yapan kişi veya kişileri tanımlar. Ayrıca, verdiği haberle alıcıyı memnun eden kişi veya kişileri de ifade eder. Bu kelime, topluma yeni bir şey getiren kişileri de tanımlamaktadır (M. Gökmen).

95. Reşar (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who are generous, easygoing, kind, respectable, worthy, gentlemen respected by his/their communities (M. Gökmen).

- 95.1. Reşar (Tr):** Bu kelime, cömert, uyumlu, nazik, saygın, değerli, toplumları tarafından saygı duyulan beyefendileri ve hanımefendileri tanımlamaktadır (M. Gökmen).
- 96. Revil (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are examining, analyzing, diagnosing, investigating a substance, text and subject(M. Gökmen).
- 96.1. Revil (Tr):** Bu kelime, bir maddeyi, metni veya konuyu inceleyen, analiz eden, teşhis eden, araştıran kişi veya kişileri tanımlamaktadır (M. Gökmen).
- 97. Reyer (Eng):** The word corresponds to person and people who are patient, tolerant, optimistic, well-mannered, far-sighted and cautious.
- 97.1. Reyer (Tr):** Bu kelime sabırlı, hoşgörülü, iyimser, nazik, ileri görüşlü ve ihtiyatlı kişi ve kişileri ifade etmektedir (M. Gökmen).
- 98. Rizis (Eng):** The word corresponds to heavy snow and rain.
- 98.1. Rizis (Tr):** Bu kelime yoğun kar ve yağmur yağışı anlamına gelmektedir (M. Gökmen).
- 99. Samay (Eng):** The word corresponds utopia, ideal and dream like life.
- 99.1. Samay (Tr):**Bu kelime ütopya, ideal ve rüya gibi bir yaşam anlamına gelir(M. Gökmen).
- 100. Sargev(Eng):** The term refers to the person or persons who raise awareness in a society. The word refers to the person or persons who alert the society, individuals, or students for a particular issue, assist them, and provide them with the means and opportunities to find the truth.
- 100.1.Sargev(Tr):** Bir toplumda farkındalık oluşturan kişi ya da kişileri ifade eder. Toplum, kişileri ya da öğrencileri belli bir konuda uyaran, onlara yardımcı olan ve onlara doğruyu bulmaları için imkan ve olanak veren kişi ya da kişileri tanımlamaktadır(M. Gökmen).
- 101. Sebut (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are attaining refreshment, peace and tranquility. The word is inspired by As- Seb'ut - Tivali meaning to, 'The common name of the long surahs of the Qur'ân which are namely al-Baqara, al-Imrân, Nisâ, Mâide, An'âm, A'râf and Tawbah (or Yûnus) '(Encyclopaedia of Islam, 2024)
- 101.1.Sebut (bulmak) (Tr.):** Kelime ferahlık, esenlik ve huzura kavuşmak anlamına gelmektedir. Kelime Es- Seb'ut –Tivali: "Kur'ân-ı Kerîm'in uzun sûrelerinden

Bakara, Âl-i İmrân, Nisâ, Mâide, En'âm, A'râf ve Tevbe'nin (veya Yûnus) ortak adından esinlenerek türetilmiştir “(İslam Ansiklopedisi, <https://islamansiklopedisi.org.tr/es-sebut-tuvel>) (M. Gökmen).

102. Segan (Eng): The word corresponds to declare and support an idea. The word is synonym to the words with argue, suggest and declare

102.1.Segan (Tr): Bu kelime, bir fikri beyan etmek ve desteklemek anlamına gelir. Bu kelime, tartışmak, önermek ve beyan etmek kelimeleriyle eş anlamlıdır (M. Gökmen).

103. Selaz (Eng): This word corresponds to a person or persons who serve as a messenger, envoy, or courier. This word also describes people who bring something new to society.

103.1.Selaz (Tr): Bu kelime, haberci, elçi ve kurye olarak görev yapan kişi veya kişilere karşılık gelir. Bu kelime aynı zamanda topluma yeni bir şey getiren kişileri de tanımlamaktadır (M. Gökmen).

104. Selis (Eng): The word corresponds to being tolerant and respectful to coexistence and difference.

104.1.Selis (Tr): Bu kelime, farklılıklara karşı hoşgörülü ve saygılı olmak anlamına gelmektedir (M. Gökmen).

105. Semzay (Eng.): The word corresponds to person or people who are bright, luminous, and radiant. The word can also be used for a person/people or society who possess substance and a distinctive level of talent with high potential. While the word can be used to describe expressions of the brightness of a light, a lamp, sun, or moon, it can also be used to describe a person, people, or groups who demonstrate bright talent with prominent success.

105.1.Semzay (Tr.): Kelime parlak, aydınlık, ışıltılı olmak anlamına gelmektedir. Kelime aynı zamanda cevher sahibi olan ve ayırt edici seviyede iyi bir yeteneğe sahip olan, potansiyeli yüksek kişiyi/kişileri ve toplumları tanımlamak için kullanılabilir. Kelime bir Işığın, Kandilin, Güneşin ya da Ayın aydınlığı anlamlarına da gelmektedir. Kelime aynı zamanda gelecek vaad eden, önemli başarılarla imza atacak kişiyi, kişileri ve grupları tanımlamak adına da kullanılabilir (M. Gökmen).

- 106. Serön (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are quite important. The word also corresponds to person or people who are residing in prior position.
- 106.1.Serön (Tr.):** Kelime oldukça önemli anlamına gelmektedir. Kelime aynı zamanda son derece önemli olan, ilk sırada olmak anlamına da gelmektedir. Kelime öncelikli olmak, birincil ve ilk sırada olmak anlamlarına gelmektedir(M. Gökmen).
- 107. Sinaf (Eng):** The word is synonym to congratulate.
- 107.1.Sinaf (Tr):** Bu kelime tebrik etmekle eş anlamlıdır (M. Gökmen).
- 108. Sirce (Eng):** The word is synonym to nature and natural life
- 108.1. Sirce (Tr):** Bu kelime, doğa ve doğal yaşam ile eş anlamlıdır (M. Gökmen).
- 109. Söğüç (Eng):** The word literally means to move and relocate.
- 109.1.Söğüç (Tr):** Kelime taşınmak, yer değiştirmek anlamına gelmektedir (M. Gökmen).
- 110. Sufye (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are generous. The word also corresponds to person or people who love to offer and share their possessions with the people
- 110.1.Sufye (Tr):** Kelime cömert, ikramı ve paylaşımı seven kişileri tanımlamak adına türetilmiştir (M. Gökmen).
- 111. Şarad (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are prospective.
- 111.1.Şarad (Tr):** Bu kelime, gelecek vaat eden kişi veya kişileri tanımlamaktadır (M. Gökmen).
- 112. Şigerbe (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who spill, lay and place something on the ground. The word also corresponds to person or people who drink, gulping down water, ayran, milkshake and fruit juice.
- 112.1.Şigerbe (Tr):** Kelime anlamıyla bir şeyi dökmek, sermek ve yerleştirmek anlamına gelir. Kelime aynı zamanda su, ayran, meyve suyu içmek, yudumlamak anlamlarına da gelmektedir (M. Gökmen).
- 113. Tayis (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are expert and specialist in a specific profession. The word is synonym to professional(M. Gökmen).
- 113.1.Tayis (Tr):** Bu kelime, belirli bir meslekte uzman ve uzman olan kişi veya kişilere karşılık gelir. Bu kelime, profesyonel ile eş anlamlıdır (M. Gökmen).
- 114. Talmer (Eng).** The word corresponds to student and researcher.
- 114.1.Talmer (Tr).** Bu kelime öğrenci ve araştırmacı anlamına gelir (M. Gökmen).

- 115. Temal (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who act logically and rationally by being aware of their deeds.
- 115.1.Temal (Tr):** Bu kelime, mantık çerçevesi içinde rasyonel hareket eden, farkındalık bilincine sahip ve varlığının farkında olan kişi veya kişileri tanımlamak adına türetilmiştir (M. Gökmen).
- 116. Teniz (Eng):** The word corresponds to be in a place. The word also corresponds to person or people who enrich and enliven a place where they reside.
- 116.1.Teniz (Tr):** Bu kelime, bir yerde bulunmak anlamına gelir. Bu kelime aynı zamanda, buldukları yeri zenginleştiren ve ihya eden kişi veya kişileri de ifade etmektedir (M. Gökmen).
- 117. Tepak (Eng):** The word refers to the highest point, the final destination and the ultimate goal.
- 117.1.Tepak (Tr):** Kelime en son had, en üst nokta, nihai hedef anlamına gelmektedir(M. Gökmen).
- 118. Tepuz (Eng):** The word refers to asserting and claiming an idea.
- 119. Tepuz (Tr):** Kelime savunmak ve ileri sürmek anlamına gelmektedir(M. Gökmen).
- 120. Tuniç (Eng):** The word corresponds to person or people who are handsome and beautiful.
- 120.1.Tuniç (Tr):** Bu kelime, yakışıklı ve güzel olan kişi veya kişileri tanımlamaktadır (M. Gökmen).
- 121. Tubat (Eng):** The word refers to enjoining and combining things.
- 121.1.Tubat (Tr):** Bu kelime, şeyleri birleştirmek ve bir araya getirmek anlamına gelir(M. Gökmen).
- 122. Uycak (Eng):** The word refers to person or people who love something, somebody by allocating their time for them. The word also corresponds to devotion of a person or community benevolently, sacrificially and selflessly to another person or community without any expectation and worldly gain
- 122.1. Uycak (Tr):** Kelime sevmek, ilgilenmek, emek vermek, vakit harcamak anlamına gelmektedir. Kelime yardımsever, fedakarca ve cefakarca bir duruma, kişiye ya da topluma kendini adanmak anlamına da gelmektedir (M. Gökmen).

123. Vanlis (Eng): The word is used for someone who is victorious. The word can also be used for someone who is the first in a competition.

123.1.Vanlis (Tr): Kelime başarılı olan kişiler için kullanılır; kelime ayrıca yarışmada birinci olan kişiler içinde kullanılabilir(M. Gökmen).

124. Veşlik (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who accompany someone, something in a protected manner. Veşlik ensures transferring a person or an object from one place to another safely.

124.1.Veşlik etmek (Tr): Kelime birine veya bir şeye korunaklı bir şekilde aracılık, yarenlik etmek anlamına gelir. Kelime bir kişinin, nesnenin ya da kişilerin bir yerden başka bir yere korunaklı bir şekilde gitmesini sağlamak ya da güvenli bir şekilde götürmek anlamına gelir. Arapça'da eşlik etmek anlamına gelen “vesile” ile aynı anlamı taşıyor gibi görünse de veşlik etmek, kişinin veya nesnenin bir yerden başka bir yere güvenli bir şekilde ulaşmasını sağlamak anlamına gelmektedir. Nihayetinde veşlik eden kişi, kişinin ya da nesnenin korunmasını ve güvenliğini aktif bir şekilde sağlayarak bir yere ulaşmasını temin etmek anlamına gelir. Bu anlamda veli olmak, göz kulak olmak ve dost olmak ile eş anlamlı bir kelimedir(M. Gökmen).

125. Vasir (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who takes over the investments and capital through kinship or donation. This inheritance can be capital, property, business as well as culture, language and religion The word is synonym to caliph and caliphate.

125.1. Vasir (Tr.): Kelime Allah'ın yeryüzündeki temsilcisi, halifesi anlamına gelmektedir. Kendisine miras kalan kişi anlamını da karşılamaktadır. Kendinden önce yapılan yatırımları, sermayeyi akrabalık ilişkisi ya da bağış yoluyla ile üzerine alan kişidir. Akrabalık ilişkisi olmayan kişiye de arzu edildiğinde bırakılabilen miras sahibi anlamını da karşılamaktadır. Bu miras sermaye, mülk, işletme olabileceği gibi kültür, dil ve din de olabilir(M. Gökmen).

126. Vazev (Eng): The word corresponds to a person or people who perform their duties willingly with love, affection and wholeheartedly. The word also refers people who are appointed and assigned to a position or a mission.

126.1.Vazev (Tr): Bu kelime, görevlerini sevgi, şefkat ve tüm kalbiyle isteyerek yerine getiren kişi veya kişileri tanımlamaktadır. Bu kelime aynı zamanda bir pozisyona veya göreve atanan ve görevlendirilen kişileri de ifade eder (M. Gökmen).

127. Yusek (Eng): The word corresponds to trainer or trainers who grow and raise children and generations. The word can also be used to describe people who are conducting farming and animal husbandry activities

127.1.Yusek (Tr): Bu kelime, çocukları ve nesilleri yetiştiren ve büyüten eğitmen veya öğretmenleri ifade eder. Ayrıca, kelime tarım ve hayvancılık faaliyetleri yürüten kişileri tanımlamak için de kullanılabilir (M. Gökmen).

128. Yaniska(Conjunction) (Eng): The word is synonym to following conjunctions and phrases: of course, absolutely, indeed, moreover. **Usage:** You are right in your deed, yaniska I will support you

128.1.Yaniska(Bağlaç) (Tr): Kelime bağlaç olarak tabii ki, mutlaka, katılıyorum, haklısın, üstelik anlamlarına gelmektedir (M.Gökmen).

129. Zanib(p) (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who serve and work selflessly for people by assisting them in their affairs solely for the sake of Allah's approval and acceptance. The word also corresponds to person or people who develop empathy and understanding towards people.

129.1.Zanib(p) (Tr): Bu kelime, yalnızca Allah'ın rızası ve kabulü için insanlara yardım ederek, onların işlerinde onlara yardım eden ve özveriyle çalışan kişi veya kişilere karşılık gelir. Bu kelime aynı zamanda insanlara karşı empati ve anlayış gösteren kişi veya kişileri de tanımlamaktadır (M. Gökmen).

130. Zayan (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who are generous and pay special emphasis on goodness, loyalty and charity. The word also corresponds to person or people who spend their wealth for the sake of Allah.

130.1.Zayan (Tr): Kelime cömert, hayrı hasenatı seven, Allah yolunda varlığını harcayan yardımsever kişi ya da kişileri tanımlamaktadır (M. Gökmen).

131. Zeler (Eng): The word corresponds to person or people who act humorously and wittily. Zeler is a person who likes telling jokes. Zeler has a high persuasive ability and is consistent in what she/he wants it to be done.

131.1.Zeler (Tr): Bu kelime, mizahi ve esprili davranan kişi veya kişilere karşılık gelir.

Zeler, şaka yapmayı seven kişidir. Bunun yanı sıra, Zeler ikna kabiliyeti yüksek ve yapmak istediği şeylerde istikrarlı olan kişileri tanımlamaktadır (M.Gökmen).

132. Zeker (Eng): The word refers to repeating or repetition of something.

132.1.Zeker (Tr): Bu kelime, bir şeyin tekrarını veya yinelenmesini ifade eder (M. Gökmen).

133. Zerab (Eng.): The word corresponds to person or people who fearlessly defend the truth and live accordingly so as to seek the grace of Allah

133.1.Zerab (Tr): Bu kelime, Allah'ın lütfunu aramak için hakkı korkusuzca savunan ve ona göre yaşayan kişi veya kişileri tanımlamaktadır (M. Gökmen).

134. Gamay (Eng): The word corresponds to distopia.

134.1. Gamay(Tr): Bu kelime distopya anlamına gelmektedir (M. Gökmen.)